

PREPARING MIDDLE SCHOOL LEARNERS FOR FOREIGN LANGUAGE PRONUNCIATION ASSESSMENTS: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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***Abstract.** In the 21st century, learning a foreign language and being able to communicate in that language has become a very important competence. Therefore, it becomes very important for an individual who learns a foreign language to acquire the main skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) and sub-skills (grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation) in language education, but it is also clear that not much importance is given to pronunciation skill compared to other skills.*

***Key words.** Pronunciation skill, communication, language teaching, middle school learners.*

Pronunciation, which does not disturb the listeners and does not negatively affect the message to be transmitted but is easily understood, is called intelligible pronunciation. For an individual who can actively engage in English-speaking societies and communicate properly, it must be clearly known that intelligible pronunciation is a vitally important part of communication. For those who try to learn a foreign language, it seems impossible to have a pronunciation skill as native people do. In this sense, intelligible pronunciation aims to achieve successful communication and attempts to eliminate factors that negatively affect communication, such as accents. If language learners fall short of intelligible pronunciation, it is clear that they will not be able to communicate with the foreign language they are trying to obtain and will not be able to use the language properly.

The practice of teaching pronunciation skill has changed significantly in English language teaching (ELT) over time, along with various approaches. While pronunciation has been superior to grammar and vocabulary in certain language teaching methods and approaches throughout history, it has not been given much importance or even excluded in teaching practices for middle school learners. Pronunciation is considered to have nothing to do with language teaching in grammar-translation method, and some other methods based on reading comprehension, while it is considered highly important in the methods in which communication and speech are emphasized. This approach is based mainly on oral communication, and it aims to bring them to an adequate level of intelligible and achievable pronunciation so that learners can have a proper conversation in a foreign language since pronunciation forms an important part of communicative competence. However, although the comprehension of pronunciation has been determined as an important part of oral communication, pronunciation has not been taken as a separate field. The main purpose is to ensure that learners use the language and are exposed to the language as much as possible during and outside the course. In this method, pronunciation is not fully expressed as a certain dimension, and what is important is to be able to use the language and focus on meaning and comprehension rather than form. Pronunciation skill is also related to the case whether English is being taught in the context of a foreign language or a second language. Second language teaching refers to the contexts in which the language taught in the classroom is already spoken outside the classroom, while foreign language teaching refers to those where the learned language is mostly not spoken outside the classroom. It's important to be understood by others while speaking the foreign language because my profession requires teamwork. When it comes to professional communication, it was found out that there were reasons such as speaking English with foreign people, learning professional terms in English, making professional presentations using a foreign language and following innovations in foreign countries. For example, somebody said, "It's of great

importance. Since my department is universal regardless of my country, it is very important to improve myself and follow the latest developments." In addition, it was also found out that there were middle school learners who stated that pronunciation for their profession was in significant.

Considering the problems of middle school learners about their pronunciation skills and the importance they attribute to their pronunciation skills, it is clear that they need a pronunciation teaching program that will bring them a lot of benefits and contribute positively to their language learning process. It is thought that preparing such a program will also contribute to the related literature. It is also thought that if teachers put a special emphasis on pronunciation skill and care about pronunciation in their lessons as much as other skills, it will be beneficial for middle school learners.

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